

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

No11
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 1530 sahifa,
4-noyabr, 2025-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijranovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyuu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalarini tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayeva X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the Editorial Board of the newspapers "Yangi Uzbekiston" and "Pravda Vostoka", Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Candidate of Philological Sciences (PhD)

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Oilaning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar estetik tarbiyasidagi o'rni	24
<i>Abdullayeva Ma'sudaxon Abdubannayevna</i>	
Bo'lajak informatika o'qituvchilarini pedagogik faoliyatga metodik tayyorlash texnologiyalari	27
<i>Abdubannoyeva Muxlisaxon Iqboljon qizi, Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida bulutli xizmatlardan foydalanish zaruriyati	30
<i>Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich, Turdaliyeva Muslimaxon Jahongir qizi</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida fortepiano chalishni o'rgatish metodikasi	34
<i>Abduvaxobova Nilufar Abdumannon qizi</i>	
Maktabda fizika fanini o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuv	38
<i>Alinazarova Mahfuza</i>	
Tasavvufdagi "komil inson" konsepsiyasining hozirgi ta'lim tizimida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv sifatida talqini	43
<i>Aqilxonov Saidolimxon Abdurashid o'g'li</i>	
Tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlikni shakllantirish omillari va pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	48
<i>Choriyeva Gulbaxor Shotemirovna</i>	
Robototexnika fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanib mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish	53
<i>Elmonov Sirojiddin Mamadiyarovich</i>	
Xalqaro baholash dasturlarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini baholash bo'yicha jahon tajribasi	58
<i>Ergasheva S. T.</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tabiiy fanlar orqali o'quvchilarning kognitiv salohiyatini rivojlantirish	61
<i>Eshmamatova Dilnoza Jovli qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning aqliy salohiyatini oshirishda tarbiyachi mahorati	64
<i>Karimova Gulzodaxon Marufjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak texnologik ta'lim o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishni takomillashtirish	68
<i>Hojikarimova Gulasal Tadjialiyevena</i>	
Xorijiy talabalarga o'zbek tilini o'rgatishda elektron platformalar yaratish	71
<i>Jo'rayeva Matluba</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun raqamli ta'lim muhitini modellashtirish va uning samaradorlik omillari	74
<i>Komilova Z. X.</i>	
O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida muloqot madaniyati	80
<i>M. Yu. Mahkamova</i>	
Psixologiya fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va talabalarda tahliliy fikrlashni shakllantirish masalalari	86
<i>Madazizova Dilfuza Raxmatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Listening and Speaking Skills in ESP (English for Specific Purposes) Classes	90
<i>Madina Tilavova</i>	
Bolalarni maktabga tayyorlash jarayonida neyropedagogik yondashuvlar	94
<i>N. O. Saidova</i>	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalarida radiologiya fanini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning metodologik roli	99
<i>Nazarova Gulchexra Shuxratdjonovna</i>	
Ijodkorlik tushunchasining mohiyati va uning ta'limdagi roli	103
<i>Ochilova Dilbar Isroilovna</i>	
Alaliyani boshqa nutqiy nuqsonlar bilan farqli xarakteristikasi	108
<i>Oripova Zilola</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda suggestopediya metodini joriy etishning samaradorligi	113
<i>Pulatova Sitora Abdurazzoq qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejerlarining kasbiy-boshqaruv kompetentligi tushunchasi va uning tarkibiy qismlari	118
<i>Qarshiboyev Sharof Egamnazarovich</i>	
Koordinatsion qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishning yosh badmintonchilar texnik-taktik tayyorgarligiga ta'siri	122
<i>Qurbanova Ilmira Alisher qizi</i>	

Blended Learning	125
Quvandikova Xadicha	
Fizika darslarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	129
Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li	
“Qurilish jarayonlari texnologiyasi” fanida loyihalash kompetentligining tarkibiy tuzilmasi va uni raqamli ta'limga moslashtirish	135
Raxmonova Nazokat Umaraliyevna	
Vitagen texnologiyalar asosida talabalar mediamentalitetini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellekt (AI) dasturlaridan foydalanishning tahliliy modeli	140
Rustamova Nodira Rustamovna	
Talabalarda kooperativ ta'lim asosida motivatsiyani rivojlantirish usullari	145
Sitora Toshmatova	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishning zaruriyati	149
Tashibekova Munajat Xoshimovna	
Musiqqa ta'limining pedagogik asoslari va metodik tizimi	153
Toshpulatova Saida Kuzibaevna	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda eng samarali metodlardan foydalanish	158
Turdiyeva Shahzoda Eshdavlrat qizi	
Enhancing University Students' Self-Directed Learning Through Edtech Tools	161
Ulasheva Lobar	
Fanlararo loyiha ishlarini tashkil etish orqali o'quvchilarning dizayn fikrlash salohiyatini oshirish	164
Valiyeva Nargiza Athamboyevna	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojiga ega o'quvchilarning kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari	169
Xakimova Sarvinov Sharifjon qizi	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida yaratilgan ta'lim platformalari: samaradorlik tahlili va pedagogik yondashuvlar	173
Xanbabayev Hakimjon Ikramovich, Erkinov Jasurbek Hasanjon o'g'li	
Tasavvufdagi “muhosaba” va “tafakkur” amallarining o'z-o'zini refleksiya metodlari sifatida qo'llanilishi	176
Xoshimov Nuriddin Mamadaliyevich	
Milliy sport va ommaviy o'yinlarning badiiy-estetik ahamiyati	182
Yaxyayeva Sojida Abdurahimovna	
Ota-ona mehriining bola psixologiyasiga ta'siri	185
Yulchiyeva Shohsanam Dilshod qizi	
Nutq rivojlanishi orqada qolgan bolalarda qo'llaniladigan innovatsion usullari samaradorligi	189
Ahmedova Nargiza Muzaffarovna	
Факторы, сдерживающие развитие науки в контексте требований к диссертационным работам	193
Зайналов Жахонгир Расулович, Нурмухамедов Аббос Мамадалиевич, Шадманов Камолиддин Кажакджанович, Самигова Нодира Хамидуллаевна	
Структура и стратегии развития предметных компетенций	197
Наимова Мафтунабону Файзулложоновна	
Психологическая консультация: современная практика, задачи и перспективы развития	203
Раупова Шохида Ахроровна	
Подготовка будущих педагогов к инклюзивному обучению детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья: задачи и перспективы	207
Сайфутдинова Насиба Нурматовна	
Формирование иноязычной грамотности у курсантов военных вузов: социально-психологические факторы	211
Сулейманова Нилуфар Камилловна	
O'qituvchi shaxsiy kompetensiyasining mohiyati va pedagogik faoliyatdagi o'rni	214
Abdiraxmonova Guliston Muzaffar qizi	
Bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarini shakllantirish jarayonining milliy va umuminsoniy tamoyillari	218
Abdumutalipova Gulshodaxon Nurbek qizi	
Fuqarolik jamiyatida huquqiy madaniyat va uni rivojlantirish jarayonlari	221
Abdusalimova Shaxnoza Quduratullayevna	
Ta'lim menejmenti tizimida o'qituvchining nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	224
Abduxalilova Iroda Nozimxonovna	

MUNDARIJA	O'zbekistonda yoshlarni ijtimoiy-pedagogik hamkorlikda tarbiyalashda "Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasi"ning ustuvor vazifalari 229 Abirova Umida Nazarovna
So'z	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida differensiyalashtirilgan dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishga o'rgatish (kompetentligini shakllantirish/rivojlantirish) usullari..... 232 Adhamova Diyora Sanjar qizi
So'z	Musobaqa faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda sambochilarning energiya sarfi va tiklanish mexanizmlari tahliliy 239 Tangriyev Abdukarim Tovashevich
So'z	Aksiologik yondashuv asosida bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining harakat faolligini takomillashtirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyati 244 Hafizov Shahriyor Shavkatovich
So'z	Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning transversal: tanqidiy va innovatsion fikrlash kompetensiyalari 248 Jaloliddinova Maftunaxon Mahmudjon qizi
So'z	Axborotning gnoseologik mohiyati 256 Kamolova Munajatxon Jaloldinovna
So'z	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish yo'llari 259 Mamatova Aziza Bo'riboevna
So'z	Akademik litseylarda kimyo fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari 262 Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich
So'z	Pedagogik oliy ta'limda talabalarning kasbiy ijtimoiylashuvini korporativ madaniyat asosida rivojlantirish metodikasi..... 267 Maxkamova Dilafuz Aliyevna
So'z	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda lingvomadaniy yondashuv 271 Normamatova Kamola Gulmamat qizi
So'z	O'zbek tili izohli lug'atida iboralarning grammatik tavsifi (bosh komponentli iboralar misolida)..... 274 S. Sh. Azamatova
So'z	Oila instituti va gender tenglikni ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-huquqiy muammolari 277 Salayeva Aziza Muhammadmurot qizi
So'z	Gender yondashuv asosida talaba-qizlarda tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning namunaviy mezonlari 282 Xolova Mohigul Shavkatovna
So'z	Pedagogika yo'nalishi talabalari huquqiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish metodlarini takomillashtirish 287 Xudoyberganov Atham
So'z	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida leksik komponentlikni TRIZ texnologiyasi yordamida rivojlantirish 291 Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Fayzullayeva Nazokat Uchqun qizi
So'z	Цифровизация и трансформация образования как социально-педагогическое явление 295 Кадирова Наргиза Азаматовна
So'z	Методика формирования креативного мышления у студентов-филологов на основе проблемно-ориентированных заданий (на материале английского языка) 298 Мамырбаева Дина
So'z	Bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari 304 Mamadjonova Sakina Mo'minjonovna, Maxmudova Oygul Toxirjonovna
So'z	Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda morfologik kompetentlikni shakllantirish 309 Ganiyeva Shodiya Azizovna
So'z	Модель "4+1+1" как ключевой механизм в системе практической подготовки учителей музыки..... 313 Мухитдинова Малохатхон Саиджабборовна
So'z	Tarbiya fanini o'qish samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish 317 Nazarova Nasiba Abdullayevna
So'z	Tarbiyachining kasbiy psixologik xususiyatlari 320 Shamshetova Anjim Karamaddinovna
So'z	Boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya nazariyasi va metodologiyasi 323 Bo'ronova Iroda Bo'ronovna
So'z	Yosh dzyudochi qizlarning mashg'ulotlar jarayonida jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish texnologiyalari 327 Matmuratova Iroda Baxtiyor qizi
So'z	"Odob us-solihin" asarida yoritilgan axloqiy-didaktik g'oyalar va uning pedagogik mazmuni 332 A. N. Nusratov
So'z	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini kasbiy kompetentligini takomillashtirishning metodik asoslari 336 Xolmatov Pardaboy Qoraboevich, Abdurasulova Dilnoza

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari faoliyatida loyihalashtirishning o'rni	342
<i>Abdusattorova Go'zalxon Abdulxabib qizi</i>	
Tibbiyot va frazeologiya inson omilida	346
<i>Achilov Muzaffar Norquliyevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida fazoviy tasavvurlarni rivojlantirishda matematikaning ahamiyati	349
<i>Mamasaidova Muhabbat Abdulalom qizi, Akbaraliyeva Marjona Xurshid qizi</i>	
Ekoestetik kompetensiyani shakllantirishning xorijiy va milliy tajribalar tahlili	354
<i>Alijonova Maftuna Maxamadjon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik jarayonda talabalarda qadriyatli munosabatlarni shakllantirish mexanizmlari	359
<i>Alikulova Muxayyo Sherovna</i>	
Ingliz ritsarlik romanlarining lingvopoetik tahlili	362
<i>Durdona Boychayeva, Aliyeva Elmira</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda estetik tarbiya berishning pedagogik asoslari	365
<i>Altibayeva Gulbaxor Majitovna</i>	
Kasbiy kompetensiya tushunchasining mazmuni mohiyati va tarkibiy tuzilmasi	369
<i>Axmadjonova Jasmira Jamshid qizi</i>	
Developing Writing Competence Among CEFR B1 and Ielts Learners Experiencing Difficulties in English Language Acquisition	374
<i>Ayturayev Majid Mavlankhanovich</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida ijtimoiy intellektni rivojlantirishning milliy qadriyatlarga asoslangan modeli	378
<i>Azamov Umarxon Yaxyoxonovich</i>	
Complications in Teaching Argumentative Speech to Students in Grades 8–9	383
<i>Buribayeva Aziza Ismatillaevna</i>	
Interfaol o'yinlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-emotsional ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari	386
<i>Buriyeva Aziza Nematovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning ijodiy faolligini shakllantirish	390
<i>Davronova Sevinch</i>	
O'quvchilarda milliy va umummadaniy kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda maqollardan foydalanish bo'yicha manbaalar tahlili	394
<i>Boltayeva Barno, Eliboyeva Surayyo Abdulkarim qizi</i>	
Social Roots and Psychological Consequences of Domestic Violence	399
<i>Dumarova Gulmira Kozimbekovna, Mamadaliyeva Gulmira, Sultonova Zulhayo</i>	
The Transversal-Methodical Competence of a Preschool Educator is the Foundation of Effective And Quality Education	402
<i>Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin kizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning innovatsion yo'llari	406
<i>Erkinova Mehriniso Ro'ziboyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini oshirish strategiyalari	411
<i>Eshonkulova Hilola Rajab qizi</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi muloqotning bilish faoliyatiga ta'siri	415
<i>Habibova Shyira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida o'qish buzilishlarini aniqlash va bartaraf etish	419
<i>Ikromova Sarvinoz Siroj qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda riskologik kompetentlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	424
<i>Jabborova Dilafuz Furqatovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda chet tili o'rganish jarayonida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning psixologik asoslari	428
<i>Jurayeva Sug'diyona Shamsiddin qizi</i>	
Transforming Education: The Impact of Emerging Technologies on Modern Pedagogical Practices	431
<i>Kadirova Ferangiz Himmatillo qizi</i>	
Salomatlik etikasi konsepsiyasi va pedagogik madaniyat – talabalar ma'naviyati va dunyoqarashini shakllantirishdagi roli	435
<i>Kamalova Yoqutxon Bahodirovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Tarbiyachilarning kasbiy mahoratini takomillashtirish va pedagogik faoliyat samaradorligini oshirish omillari 439 Kenjayeva Dildora Terkashevna Maktab ta'lim tizimida innovatsiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati 443 Kistabayeva Gulchexra Djurakulovna Kichik maktab yoshi davrida o'quv faoliyati va o'quv motivlarining shakllanishi 448 Latifa Zarifovna Korayeva Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimining raqamlashtirilishi: xalqaro tajriba va istiqbollar 451 Mahmudova Zulfiya Homidovna, Hoshimova Dilnoza Boymirzoevna Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini dizayn tafakkurga o'rgatishda STEAM yondashuvining didaktik imkoniyatlari 454 Mamadaminova Munisa Maxmudjon qizi, Boboxonova Shodiyona Rustam qizi Tabiatni asrash – kelajakni asrash: Buxoro misolida 459 Mardonova Saodat Muzaffarovna Bo'lajak pedagoglarda o'z-o'zini baholash kompetentligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish 463 Meyliyeva Nafosat Gulomovna Sun'iy intellektning ta'limda kognitiv va metakognitiv jarayonlarga ta'siri 466 Murodov Ulug'bek O'tkir o'g'li Maktabgacha ta'limda inklyuziv ta'limning tashkil etilishi 470 Mustofoyeva Muhabbat Husniddin qizi The Effectiveness of Art Therapy in Working With Children Experiencing Emotional Stress 473 Nargiza Khayrullayevna Ortikova, Laziz Azizovich Normuratov Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyalanuvchilarining musiqiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari 477 Ortiqov Akmaljon Abdusalom o'g'li CLIL metodining O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida qo'llanilishi 481 Qarshiyeva Sarvinoz Ural qizi The Use of Mobile Apps to Build Vocabulary Proficiency 486 Kosimov Sunnat Ravshan ugli Yoshlar tafakkurini rivojlantirish va ma'naviyatini oshirishda tasviriy san'atning o'rni 490 Quvonchbek Abduxamidov Axborot texnologiyalari ta'sirida san'at tushunchasining o'zgarishi 494 Rajabova Laylo O'tkir qizi Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari 498 Ramozonova Bahoroy Sadriddinovna Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlarning pedagogik asoslari 501 Yusufzoda Shabnami Yunus, Rashidova Saida Ravshonbek qizi Axborot texnologiyalarini fizika darslarida qo'llash 506 Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li Axborot xavfsizligini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish afzalliklari 510 Raxmetova Lazzat Eshitishda nuqsonli bo'lgan bolalarning psixologik xususiyatlarining o'ziga xosligi 513 S. A. Mamatisayeva Androgogik yondashuvning integrativ metodikasi 517 Sattorova Shaxlo Axadovna Gendered Language in Uzbek and English Media Discourse 520 Sultonova Charos Iskandar kizi Maktabga tayyorlov yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy ekologik dunyoqarashni shakllantirishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar 527 Suyunova Matluba Abdusaidovna Empatiya shifokor–pasiyent munosabatida: tibbiyot talabalarining psixologik tayyorgarligi 531 Tajiboyeva Odinoxon Rustamjon qizi, Qurbonova Fotima Farhodjon qizi Modern Approaches to Teaching Grammar 534 Tuychiyev Azamat Farkhod ugli The Importance of Psychological Preparation of Preschool Children for School Education 538 Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li
-------------------------------------	---

Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachi-pedagoglarining kasbiy-axloqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish	541
<i>Xabibullayeva Sayyoraxon Maxamadali qizi</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan va sog'lom bolalar faoliyatida universal ta'limning imkoniyati	544
<i>Xolmatova Sarvinoz Raxmatilla qizi</i>	
Kurashchilarning umumiy va maxsus sport tayyorgarliklari.....	548
<i>Xudoyberganov Javlonbek Soatboy o'g'li</i>	
Tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarida ekologik kompetentlik tushunchalarini rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	551
<i>Yarova Gulhayo Fazliddin qizi</i>	
Arxitektura va dizayn yo'nalishi bitiruvchilarini kasbga yo'naltirish vositasida axborot almashish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	555
<i>Kuchimov M. K.</i>	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidlarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirish metodikasi (Temurbeklar maktablari misolida)	559
<i>Quldashev Murodjon G'aniyevich</i>	
Лингвистическое исследование влияния социальных сетей на синтаксические изменения в языке современного поколения.....	562
<i>Шавилова Наталья Сергеевна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining nutq madaniyati.....	566
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna, Gulimbayeva Barno</i>	
Особенности гражданского воспитания обучающихся в системе "школа–махаля" в Узбекистане ...	570
<i>Хайдаров Шавкат Шамсиддин угли</i>	
Mantiqiy masalalarni bajarishning metodik usullari	575
<i>Tosheva Yulduz</i>	
Bo'lajak ofitserlarni harbiy-vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashda pedagogik-psixologik omillar (jamoat xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'linmalari misolida)	579
<i>Yarmatov Akbar Normurotovich</i>	
Yosh harbiy xizmatchi ofitserlarda muloqot madaniyatini samarali shakllantirish muammosining xorijiy tadqiqotlardagi talqini	582
<i>Matyakubov Elyor Rajapovich</i>	
Umumiy pedagogika fanini o'qitishda formativ baholash metodikasini joriy etish texnologiyasi	586
<i>Sobitjon Xalimov Hoshimjonovich</i>	
Формирование компонентов эмоционального интеллекта у детей дошкольного возраста с дефектами речи на основе сказкотерапии	590
<i>Эркинова Фазилат Миразиз қизи</i>	
O'zbekistonda asalarichilikning rivojlanishi.....	593
<i>Abdullayeva Maxsudaxon To'lanovna</i>	
14–16 yoshli dzyudochilarda hujum kombinatsiyalari va ularni musobaqaviy sharoitda qo'llash usullarini takomillashtirish.....	596
<i>Abduraxmanova Iroda Xayrullayevna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda aksiologik tarbiya mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish ijtimoiy ehtiyoj va pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	602
<i>B. S. Siddikov</i>	
Sport mashg'ulotlar davomida mushak va suyak tizimi rivojlanishi	606
<i>Bo'ronova Habiba Erkin qizi</i>	
Stol tennis o'yini texnikasi.....	609
<i>Ibragimov Abduqahhor Abdulaziz o'g'li</i>	
Biologiya fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy platformalarning afzalliklari: Wordwall, Educaplay, Blooket, Genially, Kahoot platformalari	613
<i>Kalandarova Dilnoza Samandarovna, Qodirova Madina Nosirovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tahsil olayotgan paraarmrestlingchi talabalarni musobaqa oldidan texnik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish	617
<i>Karimov Faxriddin Xurramovich</i>	
Developing Critical Reading Skills Through Content-Based Instruction.....	621
<i>Mekhmonkulov Burkhon Ma'ruf ugli</i>	
Tog'li va shahar hududida ta'lim oluvchi tinglovchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini taqqoslash	626
<i>Mirjamolov Sirojiddin Xayriddinovich</i>	

Korxonada va tashkilotlarda ishchi-xodimlarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish asosida ish faolligini oshirish texnologiyasi	630
Muxametov Axmad Muxametovich	
Xalq ta'limi bo'limi rahbarlarining xalqaro baholash tizimini O'zbekiston ta'limiga moslashtirishdagi o'rni	634
Namazova Manzura Urakovna, Nodirov Dilmurod	
Digital Reading vs. Print Reading: Effects on EFL Learners' Reading Speed and Understanding	639
Rustambekova Ozoda Dilshod kizi	
Yoshlarning jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlariga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirishning samarali usullari	644
To'rayev Farrux Hakim o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalaridagi talaba-qizlarni dzyudo sport turi texnik harakatlariga o'rgatish texnologiyasi	647
Toshboyeva Munisa Bozor qizi	
Sport mashg'ulotlarda jarohatlarning oldini olish va xavfsizlik choralarini	650
Xudoyberdiyeva Elmira Botir qizi	
Задачи изучения и преподавания русского языка и литературы в общеобразовательных школах с узбекским языком обучения	654
Ахмедов Нумон	
Multimedia va infografika asosida interaktiv didaktik materiallar yaratish	658
Shirinov Feruzjon Shuxratovich, Rahmonov Ziyodillo Xusanovich	
Ingliz tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining talaffuz ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi (immitativ-taqiidiy usul misolida)	661
Jo'rayeva Dilafuz Nuriddinovna	
O'simliklarning issiqqa va qurqoqchilikka chidamliligi	664
M. Nazarov, G. Maxsudova, T. Usmonova	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning jismoniy tayyorgarligi hamda psixik jarayonlar ko'rsatkichlarining tahlili	667
Masharipova Miyassar Ichanovna	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni "Tabiat bilan tanishtirish" fani asosida tarbiyaviy faoliyatini raqamlashtirish	675
Saydullayeva Barchinoy Abduxalil qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida faoliyat yuritishga tayyorlash muammolari	678
Shaxnoza To'xtiyarova	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida o'quv resurslarini yaratishning raqamli-didaktik mazmunini rivojlantirish metodikasi	681
Shirinov Feruzjon Shuxratovich	
Umumta'lim maktablarining 9-sinf fizika darslarida tovush hodisasini anglashni tajriba orqali rivojlantirish	684
Sobirov Avazbek Anvarovich	
Emotsional intellekt tushunchasining nazariy asoslari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	689
Tajiboyeva Odinoxon Rustamjon qizi	
Portret janrini o'qitishda individual ta'lim va fanlararo integratsiyaning nazariy-metodologik asoslari	693
Xudaynazarova Ug'iloy Sharifovna	
Aqli zaif bolalarda sensomotor rivojlanishning psixologik-pedagogik xususiyatlari	696
Xudoyberdiyeva Ra'no Arabboyevna	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida estetik madaniyatni tarbiyalash metodikasi (tarbiya fani misolida)	700
Yoqubjonova Shodiya G'ayratovna	
Chizmachilik fanining turmush tarzimidagi ahamiyati va o'rni	704
Achilov Nurbek Norboy o'g'li	
O'quvchilarni musiqa san'atiga qiziqtirishda musiqa psixologiyasining roli	707
E'zozxon Qobilova	
Bolalar adabiyotini o'qitishda milliy qadriyatlarni singdirish va kreativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning innovatsion yo'llari	710
G'aniyeva Shodiya Azizovna, Abdullayeva Madinaxon Madaminjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf darsliklarida berilgan mashqlarni til kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish maqsadida tahlil qilish	713
G'anijonova Sarvinov, Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna	
O'quvchilarda global o'qish savodxonligini shakllantirishda milliy matnlar va qadriyatlar asosidagi pirls tipidagi topshiriqlar yaratish tajribasi	717
Ikromova Gulhida Axmadillo qizi, G'ofurova Dilshodaxon Toxirjon qizi	

Bo'lajak pedagoglarni intellektual rivojlantirishda pedagogik artistizmdan foydalanish texnologiyalari pedagogik muammo sifatida	720
<i>Karribayeva Lobarxon Fayzulla qizi</i>	
Ilmiy matnni o'qib tushunish va baholashda nostandart testlardan foydalanish bosqichlari.....	724
<i>Komilova Lola Nasilloevna</i>	
Dizartriya davosida tovushlar talaffuzidagi kamchiliklarni o'yin orqali rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	728
<i>Mamatova Muzayyana Batirovna</i>	
Turkiy bitiklarda nomlar tizimi va ularning semantik xususiyatlari	732
<i>Munisa Shavkatova</i>	
Kommunikativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarni mediatorlik faoliyatiga tayyorlash texnologiyasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	736
<i>Muqimova Dilbarxon Xusanboyevna</i>	
Sportda liderlik va jamoaviy ruhni shakllantirish metodlari	740
<i>Nazarov Nursultan Safarbayevich</i>	
Dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishda loyihalashtirishning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	744
<i>Normurodov Sharofiddin Muxiddinovich</i>	
Ta'limda innovatsion kompetentlikning ahamiyati.....	748
<i>Qobilova Aziza Tursunovna</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari orqali bolalarda tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish	752
<i>Salimova Aziza Sharipovna</i>	
Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda masofaviy ta'limning imkoniyatlari va muammolari	755
<i>Sidiqova Ma'mura Adhamjonovna</i>	
Til kompetentligini rivojlantirishda vizual materiallardan foydalanishning o'rni (boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini oshirish texnologiyasi misolida)	758
<i>Zokirova Sohiba Muhtoralievna, Sobirova Diloromxon Ma'rufjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi ko'xlear implantli bolalarni eshituv - nutqiy reabilitatsiyasi	761
<i>Xamraeva Dildora Baxadirovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda duduqlanishni kelib chiqish sababalari va korreksion ishlar	766
<i>Xolboeva Ruxsora Egamberdiyevna</i>	
Эффективность арт-терапии в обогащении словарного запаса у детей с ЗПП	770
<i>Наган Олеся Талгатовна</i>	
Autizmli bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda o'yinning ahamiyati.....	775
<i>Nishonova Sevara</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda disgrafiyasi bo'lgan o'quvchilarda yozish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari (XIX–XXI asrda).....	778
<i>Qaxxorova Saidaxon, Mamarajabova Zulfiya</i>	
Autizmli bolalarda kommunikativ muloqotni shakllantirish texnologiyalari.....	781
<i>Raxmonova Manzura Maxmudovna</i>	
Talabalarda ma'naviy ongning rivojlanishidagi milliy dunyoqarash va tafakkur uslubining shakllanish omillari	785
<i>Usarova Nigora Berdiyevna</i>	
PIRLSda qo'llaniladigan yuqori darajadagi tushunish ko'nikmalari (interpretatsiya, sintez) va ularni muloqotga o'rgatishda qo'llash	788
<i>Choriyeva Valida Abdug'ani qizi, Shodiyev Faxriddin Teshayevich</i>	
Prokrastinatsiya fenomenining retrospektiv talqini	795
<i>M. L. Aripova</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda millatlararo totuvlikni shakllantirishda badiiy adabiyotning o'rni.....	799
<i>Xudoyberdiyeva Madina Abdulbaki qizi</i>	
Malakali futbolchilarni tayyorlashning innovatsion pedagogik va texnologik uslublari.....	802
<i>Maxmudov Mamat Raxmatovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda madaniy qadriyatlarga hurmat hissini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	807
<i>Adolat Xolmatova Muxammadjonovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda inklyuziv qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda maxsus pedagogikaning o'rni	811
<i>Alijonova Dilorom Azamjonovna</i>	
Sportning kurash turi tarixi, nazariy asoslari va zamonaviy rivojlanish yo'nalishlari.....	815
<i>Do'stov Dilmurod Karimovich</i>	

MUNDARIJA SOÐERJANIE CONTENTS	O'quvchi qizlarni oliy ta'lim muassasalariga yo'naltirishda ota-onalar bilan ishlashning kollaborativ usullari 818 Egamberdiyev Umidbek Xo'jayevich
	The Effectiveness of Art Therapy in Working With Children Experiencing Emotional Stress 821 Ortikova Nargiza Xayrullayevna, Normuratov Laziz Azizovich
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tovush talaffuzi buzilishining turlarini va darajasini aniqlash usullari 826 Otaboyeva Nodira Qodir qizi
	Ta'limda innovatsion kompetentlikning ahamiyati 830 Qobilova Aziza Tursunovna
	Intellectual madaniyatni rivojlantirishda integrativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash texnologiyalari 833 Qurbonov Jasurbek Akmaljonovich
	Biologiya, kimyo va geografiya fanlarni o'qitishda iqtidorli o'quvchilarda ekologik madaniyatni shakllantirish 837 Sultanova N. B., Toshpo'latova N. I., Azimov B. I.
	Методика развития навыков самостоятельного обучения учащихся с помощью онлайн-образовательных платформ 840 Суяров Хуршид Бахриддинович
	Oliy ta'limda sun'iy intellektni boshqarishda rivojlangan chet davlatlar tajribasidan foydalanish usullari 844 Tajetdinova Gulnara Abatbay qizi
	Variativ yondashuv asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida dialogik nutqni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari 852 Turapova Ra'no Barat qizi
	Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida tarbiyalanuvchilarga og'zaki hisoblashni o'rgatish 857 Jurayeva Muhayyo Nematillayevna
	Trening jarayonidagi muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari 861 Nodirova M. B., Usmanova S. A., Vaxidova U. A.
	Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida tahsil olayotgan talabalarining sport faoliyati turlari orqali innovatsion texnologiyalarini takomillashtirish 865 Turdiyev Umidjon Kamoliddinovich
	Badiiy adabiyot vositasida nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda dialogik nutq shakllarini shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari 868 Umarova Muhayyo Abdusattor qizi, Mamarajabova Zulfiya Narboyevna
	The Role of Family Support in Fostering Individual Resilience Against Social Offenses (An Integration of Continuing Education, National Values, and Personal Narratives) 873 Khoshimov Lutfullo Khabibullo ugli
	Milliy kiyimlarni zamonaviy material va konstruksiya bilan uyg'unlashtirish 877 Yuldasheva Gulsanam Arken qizi
	Преподавание русского языка в школах Узбекистана глазами будущих педагогов 881 Бахриева Шахноза Давроновна
	Методологические основы дисциплины "Госпитальной педагогики" 886 Равшанова Иноят Эркиновна
	Тропеический блок как ключевой инструмент создания образа восприятия в романе С. Моэма "The Razor's Edge" 889 Тагаева Тамара Баходировна
	Zamonaviy oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim va tarbiya integratsiyasi 892 D. S. Zokirova
	O'quvchi qizlarni oliy ta'lim muassasalariga yo'naltirishda ota-onalar bilan ishlashning kollaborativ usullari 895 Egamberdiyev Umidbek Xo'jayevich
	Umumta'lim maktablarida kimyo fani o'qitishning samarali usullari 898 Yunusov Mirzoxid Mirzakarimovich, Odilova Feruzabonu Oybek qizi, Soibjonova Gulasalxon Farhodjon qizi
	Ertak qahramonlari obrazlari orqali boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini axloqiy va kreativ fikrlash sifatlarini shakllantirish 901 Ortiqova Zulfiya Nurmuhammedovna, Dilnavoz Tojiyeva Abduvohid qizi
	Raqamli o'quv muhitida multimedia kontentini loyihalashning didaktik tamoyillari 905 Rustemov Muxamed Biysenbayevich
	The Essence and Content of The Concept of Ecological Culture 908 Sa'dullayeva Zuhra Murodullayevna

Talabalarda raqamli refleksiyaning shakllantirishi pedagogik muammo sifatida	912
<i>Salixova Muhayyo Shakirovna</i>	
Kasbiy leksik kompetensiya metodikasi shakllanishining tarixiy rivojlanish asoslari	915
<i>Tog'ayeva Maxfuza Abdunazarovna, Tilovova Gavhar Abdaxatovna</i>	
Autizm spektori buzilishi bo'lgan bolalar tavsifi.....	920
<i>U. M. Utbasarova</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida qo'llaniluvchi sun'iy intellekt vositalari haqida tushuncha	925
<i>Xakimova Yoqutxon Toxirjon qizi, Pulatova Ziyodaxon Baxodirjon qizi</i>	
Проблемы перевода медицинских терминов: сложности и ошибки, возникающие при переводе медицинской литературы с других языков на русский.....	928
<i>Алибекова Лайло Рахмановна</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorining mediakompetentligini integrativ yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish: model, metodologiya va empirik natijalar	931
<i>Asqarxo'jayeva Movluda Saidmuhammadzokir qizi</i>	
Identifying the Cause of Addiction to Alcohol and Drugs.....	935
<i>Nauruzbaeva Ayjan Sarsenbaevna, Reymov Muxamedali Kengesbayevich, Kalmuratova Sara Umirzakovna</i>	
Methods of Utilising the Legacy of Eastern Thinkers in Education.....	938
<i>Raimova Nasiba Abdreimovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda pedagogik muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirishda mediasavodxonlikning ahamiyati.....	942
<i>Raximova Zulfiyaxon Xashimjonovna</i>	
Pedagog va maxsus psixologlarni hamkorlikda tayyorlash texnologiyasining tarkibiy komponentlari va ularning xususiyatlari	949
<i>Turg'unov Mirjalol Mirzahamdani o'g'li</i>	
Og'ir vazn yo'qotish (weight cutting)ning organizm fiziologiyasiga salbiy ta'siri	952
<i>Ibragimov Azizbek Ilhom o'g'li</i>	
Языковая политика и её влияние на статус русского языка в образовательной среде Узбекистана ..	956
<i>Бобаназарова Шоира Содиковна, Нурмаматов Бобур Ботирович</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt didaktik ta'limot vositasi sifatida ahamiyati	961
<i>To'raboyeva Mahliyo Qo'zimbek qizi</i>	
Embracing Diversity in the Classroom: Inclusive Education Strategies for Empowering All Learners	964
<i>Bahronova Maftuna Farhadovna</i>	
Ta'lim jarayoniga xalqaro pedagogik tajribani samarali joriy etish: usullar va yondashuvlar	968
<i>Xakimov Sodiqjon Rasuljon o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarning umumdaniy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik jarayonning shakllari, vositalari, usul va metodlari.....	972
<i>Abdiramanov Bahodir Sag'iydullaevich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni zararli odatlarga qarshi kurashga tayyorlashning amaliy holati va tahlili	975
<i>Abdulazizova Nilufar Abdurahmonovna</i>	
Ekologik ta'lim-tarbiyani amalga oshirish mexanizmlari orqali talabalarda ekologik ongni shakllantirish.....	980
<i>Abdullayeva Umidaxon G'ulomidinovna</i>	
Tayyorlov guruhi bolalarining tasviriy qobiliyati va ijodkorligini rivojlantirish	983
<i>Abdumuhitorova Mohlaroy Baxtiyorjon qizi</i>	
Psixologik va pedagogik nuqtai nazardan sanogen va patogen tafakkur mexanizmlari	986
<i>Abdushukurova Mushtariy</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda estetik tarbiya berishning mazmuni va shakllari	991
<i>Altibayeva Gulbaxor Majitovna</i>	
Methods of Developing Linguocultural Competence Through Teaching Color Concepts	997
<i>Arabova Gulnir Yuzboy qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarda hayotiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish zarurati.....	1000
<i>Axunbabayeva Shaxnoza Shuxratovna</i>	
Hisor ekspeditsiyasi tarixi	1004
<i>Begaliyeva Mehriniso Olimnazarovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida bo'lajak fizika o'qituvchilarini pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlashning psixologik-pedagogik asoslari.....	1007
<i>Boqiyev Sarvar Tangirgul o'g'li</i>	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalarida multimedia vositalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati	1011
<i>Bozorov Erkin Xodjiyevich, Ergashev Asqar Jong'oboyevich, Sharipov Sharofiddin Arslonqulovich</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	The Importance of Specialized Terminology in the Educational Process.....	1014
	Dilnoza Yuldasheva Bekmurodovna	
	The Problems of Linguistic Analysis of Elliptical Sentences in Modern English.....	1019
	Eshonkulov Ravshan Tokhirovich, Jurayeva Hilola Kamol qizi	
	Boshlang'ich ta'limda sintaksis materiallarini o'qitishda kommunikativ yondashuvning ahamiyati.....	1025
	G'aniyeva Shodiya Azizovna, Nabiyeva Omaxon Rahmonberdi qizi	
	Rivojlanishi sust bo'lgan bolalarning psixologik xususiyatlari.....	1028
	Hamroqulova Dilnavoz Fayziyevna, Tohirova Shaxnoza Nodir qizi	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashda pedagogik diagnostikaning o'rni va zamonaviy usullari.....	1031
	Hasanova Irodaxon Najmiddin qizi	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda taekvondoga ixtisoslashtirilgan mashqlar majmualari orqali egiluvchanlik sifatlarini rivojlantirish.....	1034
	Iminova Z. B.	
	Inklyuziv ta'lim tamoyillari, tizimi va unda o'quvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirishning ahamiyati.....	1038
	Inayatova Nargisa Nishonboyevna	
	O'quvchilarda muloqot madaniyati ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish.....	1044
	Kalmuratovna Venera Sultanova	
	Integrativ yondashuv asosida tarbiyachilarning metakompetentligini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	1049
	Kamola Abdullayeva	
	O'rta Osiyo ziyolilarining mehnat tarbiyasi haqidagi fikr-mulohazalari.....	1052
	Karimov Orif Obloqul o'g'li	
	Maktab ta'lim tizimida innovatsiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	1055
	Kistabayeva Gulchexra Jo'raqulovna	
	Competency-Based Approach to Organizing the Educational Process for Pre-Service Teachers.....	1060
	Mahkamov Abdulqodir Ismoil o'g'li	
	Jismoniy tarbiya darslarida innovatsion metodlarning ta'siri.....	1063
	Makulov Shuxratjon Zokirovich	
	Bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslar.....	1067
	Mamadjonova Sakina Mo'minjonovna, Maxmudova Oygul Toxirjonovna	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning tasviriy qobiliyati va ijodkorligini rivojlantirish.....	1072
	Mamatmo'minova Muhabbat G'afforovna	
	Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida vaqtga oid masalalarni yechishda 5E modelidan foydalanishning samaradorligi.....	1075
	Mansurova Umida Mansur qizi	
	Inklyuziv ta'limda pedagog, psixolog va ota-onalar hamkorligini takomillashtirishning innovatsion yondashuvlari.....	1081
	Matupayeva Shohsanam Zaripboy qizi	
	Sog'lom turmush tarzi – sog'lom kelajak kafolati.....	1084
	Murodov Nozimjon Olimjonovich	
	Bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikning innovatsion shakllari.....	1088
	Nafasova Jamila Turg'un qizi	
	Maktabgacha ta'limda ijtimoiy-kommunikativlikni bilingvizm vositasida shakllantirish.....	1093
	Najmiddinova Gulnoza Odilovna	
	Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida kasrlarni o'qitishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarining o'rni va samaradorligi.....	1097
	Jalilov Muhammadali, No'monova Durdonaxon Ulug'bek qizi	
	Oliy ta'limdagi matematik kurslarni umumta'lim maktabi dasturlari bilan uyg'unlashtirish modeli.....	1101
	O'rozboyev Nusratbek Ziyaddin o'g'li	
	Yosh davrlar psixologiyasi va yoshga doir xususiyatlari.....	1104
	Orifjonova Nazokat Maribjon qizi	
	Boshlang'ich sinf darsliklaridagi assosiativ mashqlar orqali o'quvchilarda tabriya tushunchasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	1108
	Ortiqova Zulfiya Nurmaxamatovna, Xomidova Roziyaxon Ilxomjon qizi	
	Nemis tili o'qitish jarayonida talabalarni innovatsion-pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlashda kreativ kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	1112
	Ostanov Askarjon Nuriddinovich	

“Ilk qadam” maktabgacha davlat o‘quv dasturining pedagogik-psixologik asoslari	1117
<i>Parnonkulova Mo‘tabar Zaynitdinovna</i>	
Ta’lim sohasida motivatsiyani oshirishning samarali usullari	1121
<i>O. I. Pirmatov, I. S. Sobirova</i>	
Boshlang‘ich ta’limda milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyaviy faoliyatni tashkil etishning pedagogik asoslari ..	1126
<i>Qurbonova Maxtuma Fazliddinovna, Xolboyeva Dildora Azizovna</i>	
Innovatsion yondashuv asosida talabalarni ijodiy izlanuvchanlik faoliyatiga tayyorlashning mavjud holati .	1131
<i>Rahmatova Barnogul Karimjonovna</i>	
Aqliy rivojlanishning o‘quvchilarda ijodiy qobiliyat rivojlanishiga ta’sirini empirik o‘rganish natijalari tahlili...	1138
<i>Rahmatullayeva Mushtariy Parda qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar ongida oilaviy munosabatlar tushunchasining rivojlanishi	1143
<i>Rahmonova Dilafroz Baxronjon qizi</i>	
Millatlararo oilalarda voyaga yetayotgan bolalarning ijtimoiylashuvi va etnik identifikatsiya jarayonining psixologik xususiyatlari.....	1146
<i>Roziqova Malika Olimovna</i>	
Fizika fanini o‘qitishda o‘quvchilarning amaliy kompetensiyasini tajribalar orqali shakllantirish	1149
<i>Sattorov Boburbek Zokirovich</i>	
Chet tili o‘qituvchilarini tayyorlash jarayonida autentik materiallardan foydalanishning o‘rni va ahamiyati ..	1153
<i>Shaxlo Xalilova, Maqsuda Turapova</i>	
Ta’lim tizimini moliyalashtirish.....	1156
<i>T. Seydemetov</i>	
Integrating Sports Terminology Into English Teaching.....	1161
<i>Tursunboyeva Latofat Tuxtamurodovna</i>	
Yuzni skanerlash asosida operatsion tizim foydalanuvchilarini identifikatsiya qilish algoritmlari va dasturiy ta’minotini ishlab chiqish.....	1165
<i>Usmonov Maxsud Tulqin o‘g‘li</i>	
The Impact of Didactic Play on the Development of Medical Students’ Visual Competence	1173
<i>Utambetova Arzayim</i>	
Bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarda valeologik kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning pedagogik tizimi	1176
<i>Xudoyberdiyev G‘iyosiddin Baxtiyor o‘g‘li</i>	
Bo‘lajak muhandislarning ilmiy-tadqiqot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish omillari	1180
<i>Xuramova Farangiz Uchqun qizi</i>	
Inklyuziv ta’lim tamoyillari va uning mazmun-mohiyati	1185
<i>Yakubjanova Muhayyo Qodirjanovna</i>	
Classical Psychoanalysis and its Modifications Among Students: Z. Freud’s Classical Psychoanalysis	1189
<i>Zebiniso Mamarajab qizi Qurbonova</i>	
Talabalarini ilmiy tadqiqot ishlariga yo‘naltirish texnologiyasi	1195
<i>Zikriyayev Faxriddin Ma‘mur o‘g‘li</i>	
Проблемы формирования математических представлений детей в дошкольных образовательных организациях.....	1200
<i>Пак Светлана Викторовна</i>	
Теоретические основы формирования навыков говорения у учащихся уровня А2	1204
<i>Сагиндиқов Алишер Алеуатдинович</i>	
Проблема готовности детей старшего дошкольного возраста к обучению в школе	1208
<i>Ширбачеева Гульчехра Шакировна</i>	
Роль оздоровительной аэробики в повышении физической подготовленности учащихся	1211
<i>Яхшиева Мехринигор Шавкатовна</i>	
Zamonaviy futbol taktikalarining rivojlanishi va jamoa o‘yiniga ta’siri	1216
<i>Mirzamatov Akramjon G‘apurjonovich</i>	
Mehnat bozorining zamonaviy talablariga mos ta’lim modellarini loyihalash va metodik asoslarini ishlab chiqish	1219
<i>Bannayev Qosimjon Qodirjonovich</i>	
Malaka oshirish jarayonida ta’lim sifatini oshirish masalalari.....	1223
<i>Amanova Durdona Kaxramonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning samarali usullari	1226
<i>Berdiyeva Muhabbat Meliyevna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda yozish ko‘nikmalarini innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida takomillashtirishda modellashtirishning ahamiyati	1229
<i>Eshbekova Gulbahor</i>	

STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasini maktabgacha ta'limda qo'llashning me'yoriy-uslubiy asoslari.....	1233
<i>G'afforova Xurriyat Yangiboyevna</i>	
Kimyo fani o'rganuvchilari ongida moddalarning hosil bo'lish jarayonining mazmun-mohiyatini ularning genetikasiga asoslab tushuntirish.....	1238
<i>Jabbarova Dilafro'z Bo'riyevna</i>	
Application of Artificial Intelligence-Based Learning Activities for Developing Critical Thinking in Teacher Training	1242
<i>Masharipova Nargiza Otakhonovna, Xudayberganova Madinabonu Quدراتovna</i>	
Yuqori malakali darvozabonlarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish uslubiyati.....	1246
<i>Maxmudov Azamjon Muxtorovich</i>	
Multimediali elektron vositalar asosida axborot texnologiyalari fanini o'qitishda STEAM ta'lim metodlaridan foydalanishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	1250
<i>Patidinova Dildoraxon Salimjon qizi, Yo'Ichiyev Shaxriyor Xusanovich</i>	
Ona tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini bilishga qiziqtirish.....	1254
<i>Pirniyazova Sholpan Oteniyazovna</i>	
Texnologiya fani o'qituvchilarining dars samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi	1259
<i>Raxmatov A'zam Ashur o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarning shaxsiy karyerasini rejalashtirish ijtimoiy-pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	1262
<i>Raxmatova Sevara Abdulloyevna, Sharapova Hilola Dusham qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida innovatsion va kreativ faoliyatlarni tashkil etishda tarbiyachi pedagogik mahoratining o'rni	1268
<i>Sattorova Maftuna Abdug'affor qizi</i>	
Interactive Methods and Activities in Teaching Foreign Languages	1272
<i>Sayfutdinova Nilufarxon Soyibjonovna</i>	
Nutq o'stirishda yozma ishlardan foydalanishga oid pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	1276
<i>Sharipova Sarvinoz Sayid qizi</i>	
Talabalarda integrativ yondashuv asosida muloqot madaniyatini rivojlantirishning afzalliklari.....	1280
<i>Usmonova Mohizoda Avazjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning refleksiv qobiliyatlarini rivojlanishda oilaning ijtimoiy faoliyati	1283
<i>Xomidova Dilorom Abduraxmonovna</i>	
Tarbiya jarayonida o'quvchilarda vatanparvarlik tushunchasini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	1286
<i>Yavkochdiyeva Dilafuz Egamqulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning ilmiy-falsafiy dunyoqarashini rivojlantirish samaradorligi	1289
<i>Yuldasheva Xusnidaxon Jumanazar qizi</i>	
Идейно-художественные особенности публицистики Ш. Рашидова и их влияние на формирование диалога культур Узбекистана и России	1293
<i>Сярова Айнур Ибодуллаевна</i>	
Axborot texnologiyalari fanida talabalarining bilish mustaqilligini rivojlantirishda foydalaniladigan tamoyillar tavsifi.....	1296
<i>Kilichev Nurulla Abbosovich</i>	
Bolaning nutqiy rivojida oilaviy va ta'lim muhitining ahamiyati.....	1300
<i>Toshmurodova Xalima Allaberdiyevna</i>	
Psixologik va pedagogik nuqtai nazardan sanogen va patogen tafakkur mexanizmlari	1303
<i>Abdushukurova Mushtariy</i>	
Zamonaviy o'qituvchi nutqiga qo'yiladigan talablar va nutqiy kompetensiyalarni baholash mezonlari.....	1308
<i>G'aniyeva Muhabbat Lutfullayevna</i>	
Формирование профессиональной компетентности будущих воспитателей дошкольных организаций на основе технологии "Сибборд": педагогические условия.....	1310
<i>Нумонжонova Фарангиз Комиловна</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishda tarbiyachining roli	1314
<i>Choriyeva Xurmo Panji qizi</i>	
Ona tili ta'limida o'quvchilarni loyiha ishi asosida baholash metodikasi	1316
<i>Bobodo'stov Yusuf Oydin o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini CALP yondashuvi asosida o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishning metodik bosqichlari.....	1321
<i>Ahmadjonova Mushtariy Bahodirjon qizi</i>	
Shifokorlar professional karerasi resurslari va ularning obyektiv ko'rsatkichlari.....	1325
<i>Arziqulov O'tkirbek Maxammatovich</i>	

Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda disgrafiyani o'rganish va korreksiyalash	1329
Azimova Aziza Baxtiyorovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kitobxonlikni rivojlantirish asosida mustaqil fikrlashga o'rgatish texnologiyalari	1333
Mirzayeva Dilafuz	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ta'limiy faoliyatlarni tahlilini olib borishda tarbiyachilar kompetentligini oshirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	1337
Fayziyeva Mabudaxon Muxammadjonovna	
Eshitishida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarning ruhiy rivojlanishi qonuniyatlari	1342
Haydarov Islomjon Hatamjon o'g'li	
Maktab yoshidagi bolalarda jismoniy faoliyatning sog'liq va rivojlanishga ta'siri	1346
Ibragimov Xasanboy Abdusalomovich	
Kimyo darslarida raqamli resurslardan (simulyator va virtual laboratoriya) foydalanish metodikasi.....	1349
Ishmanova Zohida Ubaydullayevna, Valeeva Nailya Gennadiyevna	
The Integration of Web Technologies in Language Education	1353
Kadirova Feruza Hikmatullayevna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining yangi avlod darsliklaridan foydalanish kompetensiyasi.....	1357
Kosimova Gullola Mullajonovna	
Evaluation of the Knowledge of a Future Education Teacher on the Methodology of Teaching and the General Features of The Theory of Education.....	1360
Nishonova Munira Yakubjonovna	
Zamonaviy jismoniy tarbiya sohasining muhim jihatlari va asosiy elementlari	1364
Mamirova Dilorom Tavakulovna	
Inklyuziv ta'lim tuzilishi ijtimoiy fenomen sifatida	1367
Meliboyev Tavakkal Turg'unovich	
Yangi O'zbekistonda maktab ta'limi va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasini tashkil etishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	1371
Mexmonov Ismat Toshpo'latovich	
Pedagogning kasbiy kompetentligi va kreativ rivojlanishi.....	1375
Mirsagatova Nargiza Sayfullayevna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy immunitet va milliy o'zlikni shakllantirishning zamonaviy pedagogik asoslari	1379
Mo'minov Durbek No'monovich	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi duduqlanuvchi bolalar bilan psixokorreksion ishlarni tashkil etishda maxsus terapiyalardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari	1383
Niyozova Husnida Obidjon qizi, Mamarajabova Zulfiya Narboiyevna	
Redefining the Teacher's Role in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: Balancing Human and Machine Intelligence in ELT	1386
Nizomov Feruz Raxmon o'g'li	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida matn ustida ishlashda didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish.....	1389
Nurmonova Zebo Fattaxovna	
Bolalar, o'smirlar, o'spirinlarga kutubxona – axborot xizmati ko'rsatish.....	1392
O'ktam Nosirov	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi sensor alaliyali bolalarni eshituv nutqini o'stirish texnologiyalari.....	1398
O'zganova Dildora Xolmirza qizi, Mamatkulova Lobar Tolibjonovna	
Bolalar uchun tushunarli tilda yozilgan qiziqarli tarixiy hikoyalar, afsonalar va rivoyatlar ularning tasavvurini rivojlantirishda, shuningdek rasmlar va fotosuratlar haqida ma'lumot berishda muhim ahamiyatga ega	1402
Qodirova Buzulayho Turg'unovna	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidchilarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirishning didaktik ta'minoti	1405
Quldashev Murodjon G'aniyevich	
Ta'lim tizimida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish etikasi va tamoyillari	1409
Raximbayeva Feruza Rustamjon qizi	
Tarbiyaviy ishlarni tashkil etishda sinf rahbariga qo'yiladigan zamonaviy talablar	1412
Saytbekova Svetlana Saylaubayevna, Kuandikova Kamila	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida talabalarning axborot almashuv va xavfsizlik madaniyatini rivojlantirish metodikasi (kompyuter injiniringi yo'nalishi misolida)	1416
Solijanov Muxammad-Ali Omonillo o'g'li	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Bo'lajak ofitserlarda ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik ahamiyati (ingliz tili mashg'ulotlari misolida).....	1419
	Sotkulova Dildora Odinabekovna	
	Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida zoonimik xususiyatni ifodalovchi maqollarning lingvokulturologik xususiyati	1423
	Shaxlo Xalilova, Sug'diyona Sherqulova	
	Ona tili darslarida o'quvchilarni kreativ fikrlashga o'rgatish	1427
	Voxidova Muqaddas Rasuljon qizi, Jabborova Farida	
	Mustaqillik davrida qizlar tarbiyasining pedagogik asoslari va zamonaviy tendensiyalar	1430
	Xakimova Nargizaxon Boxadirdjonovna	
	Pedagogik ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalari uchun darsdan tashqari o'quv-tarbiyaviy faoliyatga tayyorlash modeli	1436
	Yunusova Diloramxon Abdumajitovna	
	Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida koxlear implantli o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy-muloqot kompetensiyalari	1440
	Aripova Nodira Shuxratovna	
	Методы развития устной речи детей дошкольного возраста	1444
	Исроилова Шохсанам Учкунжон қизи	
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida badiiy asarga bo'lgan qiziqishni oshirish metodikalari	1449
	Qodirova Buzulayho Turg'unovna, Asqarova Mohidil Murodilla qizi	
	Virtual modellashtirish asosida o'quvchilarning arxitekturaviy loyihalash kompetentligini rivojlantirishning didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	1454
	Abdullayev A'zamjon Komolxanovich	
	Analitik fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda tizimli yondashuvning prinsiplari	1458
	Amanova Gulxayo Dilmurod qizi	
	O'quvchilarning savodxonlik darajasini aniqlashda xalqaro baholash (PISA) dasturlarining roli.....	1462
	Axmedova Mastura Maxmudovna, Abdumalikova Zamira Dilmurod qizi	
	O'yin faoliyatida erkinlik va maqsadlilik uyg'unligi: ijodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish omili sifatida.....	1465
	Baxriddinova Yulduz Abror qizi	
	Incorporating Culture-Sensitive Communicative Tasks in EFL Courses.....	1468
	Guzal Ismailova	
	Ingliz tilini o'rganish jarayonida mustaqil ta'limni to'g'ri tashkil qilish texnologiyasi	1471
	Ibragimova Sevara Baxodirovna	
	Masofaviy ta'lim jarayonida odam anatomiyasi va fiziologiyasi fanini o'qitish: imkoniyatlar, cheklovlar va istiqbollar	1474
	Jo'rayeva Xushro'ya Yaxyoxon qizi	
	Erta yoshda ingliz tilini o'yin va TPR metodlari asosida o'rgatish samaradorligi	1478
	Kadirova Nilufar Tursinbayevna	
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar tafakkurining individual xususiyatlarini o'rganish	1481
	Karayeva Y. X.	
	Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi.....	1484
	Nazarova Mavluda Uktamovna, Botirova Ozoda Baxodir qizi	
	Boshlang'ich ta'limda darsni samarali tashkil etishda metoddan foydalanish – ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish	1487
	Nazarova Mohigul Akmalovna, Raxmonova Fariza Suxrobovna	
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda kompyuter texnologiyalarining o'rni va ahamiyati	1493
	O'rinboeva Lolaxon O'ktamovna, Nazarov Ilhomjon Usmanalievich	
	Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ona tili fanini o'qitish kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasi (Finlyandiya va Singapur tajribasi asosida).....	1496
	Olimjonova Dilnavoz Maribjon qizi	
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida integratsiyalashgan darslarni loyihalash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	1500
	Qodirova Dilshoda Abdunabiyevna	
	Ingliz tili mashg'ulotlarida yozuv ko'nikmalarini oshirishning metodik asoslari	1504
	Qurbonova Barnoxon	
	Ta'lim tizimida marketing	1508
	T. Seydemetov	
	Xorijiy tillarning o'qitilishida boshqa tillarning roli va o'qitish metodikasi.....	1515
	Tashxodjayeva Patima Bakiyevna	

Integrating Social and Linguistic Skills in English Teaching Instruction is the Key to Improving Holistic Language Competence.....	1518
Zaylobidinova Munira Gulomovna	
Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining kimyo ta'limidagi o'rni	1523
Boltayeva Shahribonu Ahmad qizi	

INTEGRATING SOCIAL AND LINGUISTIC SKILLS IN ENGLISH TEACHING INSTRUCTION IS THE KEY TO IMPROVING HOLISTIC LANGUAGE COMPETENCE

Zaylobidinova Munira Gulomovna

Third year PhD researcher at Fergana state university

ORCID:0009-0005-9137-8766

Abstract: This article primarily discusses the integration of social and linguistic skills, as well as career guidance for students, through the teaching of English in non-governmental educational institutions in Uzbekistan. Nowadays, improving the sociolinguistic competence of young people in learning a foreign language is an urgent issue, as most educational institutions emphasize the development of students' intellectual knowledge while neglecting the skills necessary for their personal and professional success. Therefore, this article highlights the need to effectively implement a methodology for developing soft skills within linguistic competencies in the education system of Uzbekistan. Considering the high demand for non-governmental educational institutions in the country, it is essential to integrate linguistic and social skills into their curricula. The article examines the issues of reforming the educational process in existing non-state educational institutions, raising its quality to a new level, applying globally recognized innovative methodologies, and guiding students toward future professions.

Key words: sociolinguistic competence, soft skills, non-governmental educational institutions, intercultural communication, personal and professional success.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitish orqali talabalarning ijtimoiy va lingvistik ko'nikmalarini, shuningdek, kasbiy yo'naltirilishini integratsiyalash masalasi yoritiladi. Bugungi kunda yoshlarda chet tilini o'rganish jarayonida sotsiolingvistik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish dolzarb masalalardan biridir, chunki aksariyat ta'lim muassasalari talabalar intellektual bilimini rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratib, ularning shaxsiy va professional muvaffaqiyati uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'nikmalarni yetarlicha inobatga olmaydi. Shu sababli, maqolada O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida lingvistik ko'nikmalar doirasida soft skillsni samarali rivojlantirish metodikasini joriy etish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Nodavlat ta'lim muassasalariga talab yuqori ekanligini inobatga olgan holda, ularning o'quv dasturlariga lingvistik va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni integratsiyalash dolzarb hisoblanadi. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistondagi mavjud nodavlat ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim jarayonini isloh qilish, uni yangi bosqichga ko'tarish, jahon miqyosida tan olingan innovatsion metodikalarni qo'llash va o'quvchilarni kelajak kasblariga yo'naltirish masalalari yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: sotsiolingvistik kompetensiya, yumshoq ko'nikmalar, nodavlat ta'lim muassasalari, madaniyatlararo muloqot, shaxsiy va professional muvaffaqiyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается интеграция социальных и лингвистических навыков, а также профессиональная ориентация студентов посредством преподавания английского языка в негосударственных образовательных учреждениях. В настоящее время развитие социолингвистической компетенции молодежи при изучении иностранного языка является актуальной задачей, поскольку большинство образовательных учреждений уделяют основное внимание интеллектуальным знаниям студентов, недостаточно учитывая навыки, необходимые для их личного и профессионального успеха. Поэтому в статье подчеркивается необходимость эффективного внедрения методики развития гибких навыков (soft skills) в рамках лингвистической подготовки в системе образования Узбекистана. Учитывая высокий спрос на негосударственные образовательные учреждения, крайне важно интегрировать лингвистические и социальные навыки в их учебные программы. В статье рассматриваются вопросы реформирования образовательного процесса в существующих негосударственных образовательных учреждениях Узбекистана, повышения его качества, применения признанных в мире инновационных методик и ориентации учащихся на будущие профессии.

Ключевые слова: социолингвистическая компетенция, гибкие навыки, негосударственные образовательные учреждения, межкультурная коммуникация, личный и профессиональный успех.

INTRODUCTION

In the age of globalization, English continues to remain a salient value that has risen to the level of state policy in Uzbekistan. Foreign languages are emerging as one of the main tools in the development of international dialogue, scientific and technical cooperation, and cultural exchange. The importance of integrating soft skills into the English teaching process has become as essential as teaching the linguistics and grammar of the target language. Nowadays, developing communicative competence, in which learners can use language units appropriately in social situations, understand different cultural contexts, and choose suitable methods of communication, is particularly significant for intercultural communication. Sociolinguistic competence enables language learners to understand various cultural values, social roles, speech norms, and communicative conventions. Any learner engaged in communication in English must be able to correctly assess the listener's position, age, social status, cultural background, and whether the situation requires formal or informal communication. This requires not only strong grammatical and lexical knowledge of the language but also mastery of soft skills that allow the learner to complete communication effectively and with a positive attitude. This article describes how practical research demonstrates that the integration of sociolinguistic elements into English language teaching develops students' communication skills, along with important soft skills such as creativity, flexibility, critical thinking, social engagement, time management, and cultural sensitivity. This directly contributes to their success in further education and professional activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The importance of developing social skills and linguistic competence is closely interconnected in the process of learning foreign languages, and both play a crucial role in increasing an individual's success in life and efficiency in professional activities. It has become evident that even if a learner is proficient in the target language, they may still face difficulties due to a lack of soft skills. Our research has shown that the development of soft skills among learners is practically absent in non-governmental educational institutions. This situation contributes to rising unemployment and increases labor migration to other countries. N. Bahriyeva (2019), in her study among students of Bukhara State University, notes that unemployment among graduates is increasing due to insufficient soft skills training hours in higher education. Therefore, research indicates that professional training in soft skills and career guidance should begin at an earlier stage. This further confirms that the development of learners' social skills has become one of the key priorities of educational policy in many countries around the world today. According to I. Aliyev (2013), developing learners' soft skills in the process of teaching foreign languages is of great importance today, not only in increasing the efficiency of education but also in preparing qualified personnel who meet the needs of society. This approach creates opportunities for applying foreign languages in real-life situations rather than limiting them to linguistic knowledge alone. Our study of the educational system of Uzbekistan, particularly the development of sociolinguistic competence among students learning English in non-governmental educational centers, clearly demonstrates the relevance of this issue to the country's ongoing reforms and the demand for a workforce equipped with both linguistic and social competence. According to the results of a study conducted among adolescents aged 15–17 in non-governmental schools, 80% of students stated that their main goal was to enter higher education institutions, while 16% reported studying English to work or study abroad. Interviews with teachers revealed that only 17% of graduates from non-state educational centers were able to secure satisfactory income-generating employment; moreover, it was found that most alumni were working in low-income positions ^[11].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to examine the effectiveness of integrating social and linguistic skills in English teaching for improving holistic language competence. A quasi-experimental design with pre-test and post-test measures is used, where the experimental group receives integrated instruction including social interaction skills, collaborative tasks, pragmatic functions, and linguistic components such as grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation, while the control group follows traditional language teaching. Participants consist of intermediate-level EFL learners selected through purposive sampling, and data are collected through standardized language tests, classroom observations, student questionnaires, teacher interviews, and student reflective journals. The intervention lasts 8–12 weeks and includes role-plays, discussions, problem-solving activities, and project-based learning designed to merge social communication behaviors with linguistic performance. Quantitative data are analyzed through descriptive statistics and t-tests to measure learning gains, while qualitative data are examined using thematic analysis to identify patterns in learner interaction, teacher perceptions, and classroom processes. Reliability is strengthened through triangulation of multiple instruments, inter-rater scoring of speaking tasks, and pilot

testing of questionnaires, ensuring that the methodology provides a comprehensive and valid examination of how integrated social-linguistic instruction influences learners' overall language development.

The research conducted confirms that developing young people's soft skills through the educational process leads to significant economic transformations in society. Therefore, it is essential to consider the specific characteristics of soft-skills education when organizing teacher-training activities in non-governmental schools. Sociolinguistic skills refer to the distinctive features of instructional processes aimed at guiding learners toward enhancing their intellectual knowledge and socialization in an intercultural environment, as well as equipping them with the theoretical and practical knowledge needed for future professional performance.

According to D. O. Khimmataliyev (2018), sociolinguistic competences are primarily formed through intercultural education at schools, which is necessary for step-by-step planning and logical sequencing in the educational process. A systematic approach is considered the foundation of educational effectiveness (Bakhrieva, 2019). While Khimmataliyev emphasizes high-level preparation in technical and higher education institutions, this process must also be implemented in non-governmental educational institutions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

These results indicate several existing problems in the methodology of teaching second languages. First of all, some graduates of non-governmental schools claim that the lack of a special diploma from a higher educational institution is the main limitation for becoming a highly paid employee. However, the problem is not only the absence of a diploma, but also, as researcher Sh. Majid et al. (2019) noted, the lack of social skills and practical knowledge, which is one of the most obvious issues facing today's youth. This demonstrates that the development of learners' sociolinguistic approach is not sufficiently considered in the curricula of private schools. The lack of soft-skills development in these curricula leads to a shortage of personnel for 21st-century jobs that are in high demand in the labor market. For example, M. Zaylobidinova and B. Shermuhammadov (2024) argue that limiting learners from practical exercises in the process of learning English prevents students from developing their soft skills. This approach not only restricts students' opportunities to fully realize their potential, but also fails to support the strategic goals of New Uzbekistan. The innovative model of the state education standard requires young people to become qualified specialists who not only know the language, but can also effectively apply their knowledge and skills in their professional activities. Research shows that 80% of non-governmental educational centers fail to realize the full potential of their students. Most of them do not develop practical knowledge and skills aimed at professional goals in the process of learning English. As a result, students are deprived of the opportunity to effectively use their intellectual potential.

Sociolinguistic competence is the ability to use language in real communication situations in accordance with social contexts and includes aspects such as knowledge of speech etiquette, intercultural communication skills, and the appropriate selection of lexical and grammatical units. In second-language learning, developing sociolinguistic competence means developing learners' soft skills within the linguistic skills of the target language. This competence ensures that students not only know the language but also use it correctly and effectively throughout the learning process. The integration of social and linguistic skills into second-language acquisition, including practical training in culture, teamwork, communication, as well as developing critical thinking, creativity, and effective time-management skills in non-governmental schools, is essential in modern education. Students also need special training according to their chosen professional field and a clear understanding of market requirements. According to M. Zaylobidinova (2022), integrating sociolinguistic competence into second-language acquisition accelerates the learning process and aligns with Uzbekistan's education strategies. Lessons designed with sociolinguistic competence in teaching English offer several advantages: they form practical knowledge and skills, as students acquire competences relevant to their personal and professional needs. While intellectual knowledge is important, social skills accelerate learners' development as specialists in their chosen fields. Integrating sociolinguistic competence into second-language learning increases competitiveness by preparing young people as competitive specialists in the labor market. Students who acquire both linguistic abilities and soft skills significantly enhance their competitiveness in modern professional fields, including employment opportunities abroad.

Learning a foreign language also serves as an important foundation for personal development: it enables scholars and educators to access scientific literature in its original form, expanding their academic horizons. At the same time, language learning contributes to shaping individuals' social identity and worldview, forming culturally aware and intellectually mature members of society. Moreover, integrating social skills into the process of teaching a foreign language increases lesson interactivity. Such lessons naturally become more engaging for teachers as well, while interactive activities and problem-based tasks stimulate learners' active participation and help them overcome personal barriers such as shyness, reluctance to speak, or lack of self-confidence.

The rapid development of modern technologies and the acceleration of globalization are leading to the emergence of new professions. This process requires the preparation of highly skilled specialists who meet the demands of the new era. According to N. Amanlikova (2023), the main reason for the shortage of qualified personnel in our country is the insufficient development of soft skills among young people, such as creativity, communication, and collaboration. She concludes that modern specialists must be equipped with strong social skills as well as sociolinguistic competencies, and both must be developed adequately. Therefore, incorporating social and linguistic skills into the curricula of non-governmental educational centers can provide solutions to many challenges. Sociolinguistically integrated lessons can help reduce unemployment, improve living standards, and alleviate poverty. Introducing such curricula into the programs of non-governmental educational centers would allow the majority of young people in Uzbekistan to benefit from these opportunities.

Exercises that integrate sociolinguistic competencies in teaching foreign languages include role-play activities, which help learners practice dealing with real-life situations and develop appropriate strategies for interpreting and resolving them effectively. For example, students may assume various professional roles such as a doctor and a patient, a sales assistant and a customer, or a librarian and a student. The primary purpose of these activities is to cultivate essential social skills in young learners, enabling them to navigate workplace challenges with confidence. Case studies, which involve analyzing problematic situations, are also effective. These methods present real-life scenarios requiring participants to observe consequences, evaluate the effectiveness of actions, and propose solutions (Shermukhammadov, 2023). Students analyze and discuss such cases with the instructor supervising the process. Debate scenarios may also be introduced, allowing students to propose and compare potential solutions. Project-based learning develops students' ability to work collaboratively. Producing video content, for example, requires team-based responsibilities, such as filming, presenting, and editing. Successful outcomes are viewed as collective achievements. Interview and debate activities encourage learners to express their ideas freely and strengthen communicative competence. Such lessons not only help students identify their professional interests but also contribute to future career success (Zaylobidinova, 2022).

Another important component is integration, which ensures coherence between linguistic competence and social skills and supports their application in real learning environments. Flexibility involves updating English curricula according to learners' changing needs and developing the competencies required for modern education. Forming sociolinguistic competencies such as effective communication, problem-solving, teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking directly impacts students' intellectual and professional success. Integrating sociolinguistic competence into English teaching makes lessons more engaging and contributes to preparing specialists who meet societal demands. Incorporating modern technologies and teaching methods improves educational quality and ensures an interactive learning environment.

Uzbekistan's contemporary education system is increasingly prioritizing alignment with international standards. Teachers' qualifications in sociolinguistic competencies should be recognized through a certification system aligned with the goals of modern education. A well-developed certification process enhances employability by formally acknowledging acquired skills. These features, when implemented collectively, contribute to the establishment of a modern and effective education system.

In non-governmental schools, the integration of sociolinguistic competence in foreign-language teaching has become a key priority within Uzbekistan's new education strategy. This approach ensures alignment with international standards, prepares the younger generation for personal and professional success, and supports their effective integration into the global labor market. However, several significant challenges persist in non-state educational centers, including the lack of structured curricula and reliance on informal online resources. These issues have made such institutions a focal point for research. Furthermore, it has been observed that non-governmental schools, particularly those specializing in foreign languages, attract a substantial proportion of the country's youth, underscoring their critical role in national education.

CONCLUSION

Integrating linguistic competence and social skills for career guidance should become a strategic objective of the rapidly developing education system of Uzbekistan. To achieve this goal, all resources – including both governmental and non-governmental educational institutions – must be mobilized. Our research identified that non-governmental schools primarily focus on enhancing learners' intellectual knowledge for admission to higher education institutions, whereas less attention is given to developing learners' social skills. However, the integration of social skills into educational programs prepares learners for social life and guides them toward future professions. Therefore, it has been deemed necessary to give greater attention to developing specialized curricula focused on integrating social skills into foreign-language teaching and to create a corresponding educational manual based on these curricula. Furthermore, it should be noted that integrating sociolinguistic competence through the teaching of foreign languages in non-governmental schools aligns with Uzbekistan's

broader goals of preventing workforce shortages, reducing poverty, and improving the population's quality of life. Naturally, sociolinguistic integrated lessons should be enriched with teaching methods such as role-plays, case studies, project-based learning, debates, and interviews. Lessons designed in this manner must be characterized by a high level of organization, strong alignment with practical application, adaptability to labor-market demands, integration of social skills, conformity with international standards, and the presence of innovative approaches.

References:

1. Aliyev, I. T. (2013). Pedagogning kasbiy kompetentligi. In *Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchilarni kasbiy-pedagogik kompetentligini rivojlantirish muammolari va istiqbollari: Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari* (p. 55). Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU.
2. Bakhrieva, N. A. (2019). Ta'lim muassasalari mutaxassislari kasbiy kompetentligining tuzilishi. *Sovremennoe obrazovanie (Uzbekistan)*, (9)(82), 3–10.
3. Majid, S., Eapen, C. M., & Oo, K. T. (2019). The importance of soft skills for employability and career development: Students and employers' perspectives. *IUP Journal of Soft Skills*, 13(4), 7–39.
4. Khimmataliyev, D. O. (2018). *Kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorgarlikni diagnostika qilishda pedagogik va texnik bilimlar integratsiyasi (texnika oliy ta'lim muassasalari "Kasb ta'limi" yo'nalishlari misolida)* (Doctoral dissertation). Tashkent.
5. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti. (2021, May 19). O'zbekiston Respublikasida xorijiy tillarni o'rganishni ommalash-tirish faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida [Presidential Decree].
6. Shermukhammadov, S. (2023). Revolutionizing education: Exploring the world's most engaging interactive technologies and effective teaching approaches. *Pedagogia: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 12(1), 60.
7. Zaylobidinova, M. G. (2022). Globalization education in Uzbekistan: Reforming the education system in Uzbekistan with the partnership of an international organization. *Globalization*, 10.
8. Zaylobidinova, M., & Shermuhammadov, B. (2024). *Chet tili darslarida o'quvchilarda ijtimoiylashuv ko'nikmasini shakl-lantirishning ahamiyati*. Nordic Press, 5(0005), 3.
9. Zaylobidinova, M. G. (2024). Perspectives of integration soft skills into the educational system in Uzbekistan. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 2(5), 120–127.
10. Zaylobidinova, M. G. (2022). Proliferation of shadow education in Uzbekistan. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, Edu-cational, Natural and Social Sciences*.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №11

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.